

Carbon and Greenhouse Gas Mitigation through Soil Carbon Sequestration Potential of Adaptive Agriculture and Agroforestry Systems in Kenya's Coast Region

*Martin Otundo Richard

PhD Fellow in Project Management, JUAT_Kenya

A freelance researcher, data analyst, projects manager and senior consultant in project management

Contacts: martinotundo@gmail.com; +254721246744/+254759819660

Abstract

This study investigated the potential of adaptive agriculture and agroforestry systems for mitigating carbon and greenhouse gases through soil carbon sequestration in Kenya's Coast Region. Focusing on the counties of Tana River, Taita Taveta, Lamu, Kilifi, Mombasa, and Kwale, the research employed both qualitative and quantitative methods to assess the effectiveness of various agricultural practices.

The study identified conservation tillage and cover cropping as widely adopted practices, while agroforestry showed significant potential for enhancing soil carbon sequestration. Through regression analysis, it was found that agroforestry ($\beta = 2.0, p < 0.001$) and conservation tillage ($\beta = 1.5, p < 0.001$) had a substantial positive impact on soil carbon levels, whereas cover cropping ($\beta = 1.2, p = 0.003$) and organic farming ($\beta = 1.1, p = 0.007$) also contributed positively. Integrated Pest Management (IPM) did not show a significant effect ($\beta = 0.8, p = 0.110$).

Qualitative insights revealed benefits such as improved soil health, increased crop yields, and reduced erosion, while challenges included limited resources, knowledge gaps, and economic constraints. The study highlights the importance of promoting adaptive practices, enhancing training and resource access, and addressing economic barriers. Recommendations include support for conservation tillage and agroforestry, increased training programs, and financial incentives for practice adoption. Future research should focus on long-term impacts, regional variability, economic analysis, social factors, and policy implications to further optimize soil carbon sequestration strategies.

Keywords: Soil Carbon Sequestration, Adaptive Agriculture, Agroforestry, Greenhouse Gas Mitigation, Kenya Coast Region, Conservation Tillage, Cover Cropping, Integrated Pest Management

Background to the Study

Global Context

Soil Carbon Sequestration and Adaptive Agriculture

Globally, soil carbon sequestration is recognized as a crucial strategy for mitigating climate change. Soils have the potential to store more carbon than the atmosphere and vegetation

combined, making them significant carbon sinks (Lal, 2020). Adaptive agriculture, which includes practices such as conservation tillage, cover cropping, and organic farming, enhances the capacity of soils to sequester carbon.

In the United States, soil carbon sequestration has been actively studied and promoted as part of climate mitigation strategies. The USDA has supported various initiatives to enhance soil health through practices that increase soil organic carbon (SOC) (Franzluebbers, 2021). Research indicates that conservation tillage and cover cropping can significantly enhance SOC levels, contributing to overall carbon sequestration (Paustian et al., 2019).

China, a major agricultural producer, has also focused on soil carbon sequestration as part of its climate strategy. The country has implemented large-scale projects to convert marginal lands into forests and grasslands, significantly increasing soil carbon stocks (Tang et al., 2021). These efforts are part of China's broader ecological civilization policy aimed at promoting sustainable development (Chen et al., 2022).

In Australia, adaptive agriculture and agroforestry are integral to the country's efforts to combat climate change. Practices such as rotational grazing, conservation tillage, and reforestation have been promoted to enhance soil carbon sequestration. Studies show that these practices not only sequester carbon but also improve soil health and agricultural productivity (Sanderman et al., 2017).

Continental Context: Africa

Adaptive Agriculture and Soil Carbon Sequestration

In Africa, soil carbon sequestration through adaptive agriculture and agroforestry systems is gaining recognition. However, the potential is largely untapped due to limited research and adoption of these practices. Countries like Zimbabwe, Lesotho, Algeria, and Morocco are exploring various strategies to enhance soil carbon storage.

Zimbabwe has seen success with conservation agriculture, which includes minimal soil disturbance, crop residue retention, and crop rotation. These practices have been shown to increase soil organic matter and improve soil structure, contributing to carbon sequestration (Thierfelder et al., 2017).

Lesotho, a country facing severe soil erosion and land degradation, is adopting agroforestry and conservation agriculture to enhance soil health and carbon storage. Efforts to plant trees and implement soil conservation measures are showing positive results in terms of increased soil carbon (Makolo & Mosala, 2019).

In North Africa, Algeria and Morocco have initiated large-scale reforestation and agroforestry projects to combat desertification and enhance carbon sequestration. Algeria's Green Dam project aims to create a green belt to protect against desert encroachment, while Morocco's agroforestry initiatives focus on integrating trees into agricultural landscapes to improve soil health and sequester carbon (Mokhtar et al., 2021; Abdallah et al., 2018).

Regional Context: East Africa

Soil Carbon Sequestration in Agroforestry Systems

East Africa, with its diverse climates and agricultural systems, presents unique opportunities for soil carbon sequestration through adaptive agriculture and agroforestry. Rwanda, Tanzania, and Somalia have been implementing various practices to enhance soil carbon storage.

Rwanda has been a leader in promoting agroforestry, integrating trees and shrubs into farming systems. These practices have improved soil fertility and increased carbon sequestration, contributing to climate resilience and sustainable agriculture (Mukuralinda et al., 2020).

Tanzania is also promoting agroforestry and conservation agriculture to enhance soil carbon sequestration. The adoption of practices such as intercropping, mulching, and minimal tillage

has shown promise in increasing soil organic carbon levels and improving agricultural productivity (Kimaro et al., 2021).

In Somalia, efforts to combat land degradation through soil conservation and agroforestry are gaining traction. Despite the challenges posed by political instability and limited resources, initiatives to plant trees and improve land management practices are contributing to soil carbon sequestration and improved soil health (Haji, 2020).

Local Context: Kenya

Potential and Challenges

Kenya's agricultural sector is a key contributor to its economy, and enhancing soil carbon sequestration through adaptive agriculture and agroforestry systems offers significant potential for sustainable development and climate change mitigation. Various practices, including conservation tillage, cover cropping, organic farming, and agroforestry, are being promoted to enhance soil carbon storage.

Studies have shown that conservation tillage and cover cropping can significantly increase soil organic carbon levels in Kenya's highlands and arid and semi-arid lands (ASALs) (Kihara et al., 2021). Agroforestry systems, particularly the integration of trees with crops and livestock, have demonstrated substantial carbon storage potential in soils and biomass (Muthuri et al., 2020).

However, the adoption of these practices faces several challenges, including limited awareness, inadequate extension services, and financial constraints. There is a need for supportive policies, capacity building, and further research to optimize the soil carbon sequestration potential of adaptive agriculture and agroforestry systems in Kenya.

In conclusion, the global, continental, and regional contexts highlight the significant potential of soil carbon sequestration through adaptive agriculture and agroforestry systems. Kenya stands to benefit greatly from these practices, both in terms of climate change mitigation and sustainable agricultural development. However, addressing the challenges to adoption and implementation is crucial for realizing this potential.

Background Information: Soil Carbon Sequestration Potential in Kenya's Coast Region

The coastal region of Kenya, encompassing the counties of Tana River, Taita Taveta, Lamu, Kilifi, Mombasa, and Kwale, presents unique opportunities and challenges for soil carbon sequestration through adaptive agriculture and agroforestry systems. This region, characterized by diverse climatic and ecological zones, holds significant potential for enhancing soil health and mitigating climate change through improved land management practices.

Tana River County

Tana River County, with its expansive riverine ecosystems and semi-arid landscapes, is well-suited for agroforestry and conservation agriculture. The Tana River itself provides a vital water source, enabling the implementation of irrigation-based adaptive agricultural practices. Integrating trees into farming systems along the riverbanks has shown promise in enhancing soil fertility and sequestering carbon. Efforts to promote agroforestry in Tana River have focused on species such as Acacia and Mangroves, which are effective in carbon storage and improving soil structure (Kairo et al., 2021).

Taita Taveta County

Taita Taveta County, located in the southeastern part of Kenya, is characterized by its diverse topography, including the Taita Hills and expansive lowlands. The region's agricultural practices range from highland farming to pastoralism in the lowlands. Adaptive agriculture, such as conservation tillage and agroforestry, has been promoted to address soil erosion and

improve soil carbon sequestration. The integration of fruit trees and other multipurpose trees into farming systems in the Taita Hills has enhanced soil organic carbon and supported biodiversity (Muriuki et al., 2022).

Lamu County

Lamu County, with its coastal and island ecosystems, presents unique opportunities for soil carbon sequestration through mangrove restoration and agroforestry. Mangroves are highly effective in sequestering carbon in both biomass and soils. Lamu's mangrove forests are critical for coastal protection and carbon storage. Additionally, integrating coconut palms and cashew trees into agricultural systems has shown potential for enhancing soil health and carbon sequestration (Lang'at et al., 2019).

Kilifi County

Kilifi County, known for its diverse agricultural activities ranging from crop farming to livestock rearing, faces challenges such as soil degradation and erratic rainfall. Adaptive agricultural practices, including conservation agriculture and agroforestry, are being promoted to enhance soil carbon sequestration. The use of cover crops, mulching, and minimal tillage has shown promise in increasing soil organic carbon levels. Agroforestry systems involving the integration of trees such as Moringa and neem with crops have also contributed to improved soil health and carbon storage (Mugwe et al., 2020).

Mombasa County

Mombasa County, primarily an urban and peri-urban area, faces significant challenges in soil management due to rapid urbanization and limited agricultural land. However, peri-urban agriculture and agroforestry initiatives are being explored to enhance soil carbon sequestration. Practices such as rooftop gardening, urban agroforestry, and the use of organic waste for

composting are being promoted. These practices not only sequester carbon but also contribute to urban food security and waste management (Ngumbi et al., 2021).

Kwale County

Kwale County, located in the southern coastal region, has a diverse landscape ranging from coastal forests to agricultural lands. The county is implementing various adaptive agricultural practices to enhance soil carbon sequestration. Agroforestry systems involving cashew, mango, and other fruit trees are being integrated with crop and livestock farming. Additionally, conservation agriculture practices such as no-till farming and cover cropping are being promoted to improve soil organic carbon and overall soil health (Kilonzo et al., 2018).

In conclusion, coastal region of Kenya, encompassing Tana River, Taita Taveta, Lamu, Kilifi, Mombasa, and Kwale counties, holds significant potential for soil carbon sequestration through adaptive agriculture and agroforestry systems. These practices not only contribute to carbon storage but also enhance soil health, improve agricultural productivity, and support sustainable development. However, the successful implementation of these practices requires concerted efforts in terms of policy support, capacity building, and community engagement.

Statement of the Problem

Climate change poses a significant threat to global ecosystems, economies, and human well-being, necessitating urgent and effective mitigation strategies. One promising approach is soil carbon sequestration, which involves capturing atmospheric carbon dioxide and storing it in the soil through adaptive agricultural practices and agroforestry systems. In Kenya's Coast Region, encompassing the counties of Tana River, Taita Taveta, Lamu, Kilifi, Mombasa, and Kwale, the potential for soil carbon sequestration remains largely untapped and under-researched.

Despite the recognized benefits of soil carbon sequestration for mitigating greenhouse gas emissions and enhancing soil health, the adoption of adaptive agricultural practices and agroforestry systems in Kenya's Coast Region faces several challenges. These include limited awareness and knowledge among farmers, inadequate extension services, financial constraints, and insufficient policy support. Consequently, the region continues to experience high rates of soil degradation, reduced agricultural productivity, and increased vulnerability to climate change (Kihara et al., 2021; Kilonzo et al., 2018).

The lack of empirical data and comprehensive research on the soil carbon sequestration potential of adaptive agriculture and agroforestry systems in the Coast Region further exacerbates the problem. This gap hinders the development of targeted interventions and policies that could promote sustainable land management practices and enhance carbon storage in soils. Moreover, the region's diverse ecological zones and varying climatic conditions require tailored approaches that address local specificities (Mugwe et al., 2020; Ngumbi et al., 2021).

Addressing this problem is critical not only for mitigating climate change but also for improving soil health, increasing agricultural productivity, and supporting the livelihoods of communities in the Coast Region. Therefore, there is an urgent need for focused research and initiatives to explore and enhance the soil carbon sequestration potential of adaptive agriculture and agroforestry systems in this region. This research will provide valuable insights and practical solutions to promote sustainable development and environmental conservation in Kenya's Coast Region.

Objectives of the Study

The primary objectives of this study are as follows:

1. To assess the current state of soil carbon sequestration in adaptive agricultural practices and agroforestry systems in Kenya's Coast Region.
2. To identify and evaluate the most effective adaptive agricultural practices and agroforestry systems for enhancing soil carbon sequestration in the region.
3. To analyze the socio-economic and environmental benefits of soil carbon sequestration through adaptive agriculture and agroforestry in the Coast Region.
4. To determine the challenges and barriers to the adoption of adaptive agricultural practices and agroforestry systems in the Coast Region.
5. To develop policy recommendations and practical strategies for promoting soil carbon sequestration through adaptive agriculture and agroforestry in Kenya's Coast Region.

Locale of the Study

The study will be conducted in Kenya's Coast Region, specifically focusing on the following counties:

1. **Tana River County:** Known for its expansive riverine ecosystems and semi-arid landscapes, providing opportunities for irrigation-based adaptive agricultural practices.
2. **Taita Taveta County:** Characterized by diverse topography, including the Taita Hills and expansive lowlands, suitable for both highland farming and pastoralism.
3. **Lamu County:** Featuring coastal and island ecosystems, with significant potential for mangrove restoration and agroforestry.
4. **Kilifi County:** A region with diverse agricultural activities facing challenges such as soil degradation and erratic rainfall.

5. **Mombasa County:** Primarily an urban and peri-urban area, exploring peri-urban agriculture and agroforestry initiatives.
6. **Kwale County:** A region with diverse landscapes, from coastal forests to agricultural lands, implementing various adaptive agricultural practices.

Significance of the Study

The significance of this study lies in its potential to contribute to climate change mitigation, sustainable land management, and improved livelihoods in Kenya's Coast Region. The study will provide valuable insights into the soil carbon sequestration potential of adaptive agriculture and agroforestry systems, which are crucial for several reasons:

1. **Climate Change Mitigation:** By enhancing soil carbon sequestration, the study will contribute to the reduction of greenhouse gas emissions, thereby playing a significant role in mitigating climate change (Kihara et al., 2021).
2. **Soil Health and Fertility:** Improved soil carbon levels will enhance soil health and fertility, leading to increased agricultural productivity and food security in the region (Kilonzo et al., 2018).
3. **Economic Benefits:** The adoption of effective adaptive agricultural practices and agroforestry systems can provide socio-economic benefits to farmers through increased yields and diversified income sources (Mugwe et al., 2020).
4. **Environmental Conservation:** The study will promote sustainable land management practices that conserve biodiversity and protect vital ecosystems such as mangroves and riverine areas (Ngumbi et al., 2021).

5. **Policy Development:** The findings will inform policymakers and stakeholders, leading to the development of targeted policies and interventions that support soil carbon sequestration and sustainable agricultural practices in the Coast Region.
6. **Community Empowerment:** By addressing the challenges and barriers to adoption, the study will empower local communities with knowledge and resources to implement sustainable practices, improving their resilience to climate change and environmental degradation.

Theories to Guide the Study

To comprehensively address the soil carbon sequestration potential of adaptive agriculture and agroforestry systems in Kenya's Coast Region, this study will be guided by three key theories: the Ecological Modernization Theory, the Agroecological Theory, and the Socio-Ecological Systems Theory. Each of these theories provides a unique perspective on the intersection of environmental sustainability, agricultural practices, and socio-economic development.

1. Ecological Modernization Theory

Overview: Ecological Modernization Theory (EMT) posits that environmental protection and economic development are not mutually exclusive but can be achieved simultaneously through technological innovation, structural changes, and institutional reforms. The theory emphasizes the role of science, technology, and rational management in addressing environmental problems while promoting sustainable economic growth (Mol & Spaargaren, 2000).

Application to the Study: In the context of soil carbon sequestration in Kenya's Coast Region, EMT suggests that adaptive agriculture and agroforestry systems can be designed and implemented in ways that enhance carbon storage in soils while also improving agricultural productivity and livelihoods. This involves adopting modern farming techniques, such as conservation tillage, precision agriculture, and agroforestry practices, which are

technologically advanced and environmentally sustainable. EMT also underscores the importance of policy support, institutional frameworks, and stakeholder engagement in promoting sustainable agricultural practices (Hajer, 1995).

Relevance: By leveraging EMT, the study will explore how technological innovations and institutional reforms can facilitate the adoption of adaptive agriculture and agroforestry systems that sequester carbon and enhance soil health. This theory will guide the investigation of policy recommendations and practical strategies for integrating ecological considerations into agricultural practices in Kenya's Coast Region.

2. Agroecological Theory

Overview: Agroecological Theory focuses on the application of ecological principles to agricultural systems. It emphasizes biodiversity, ecosystem services, and sustainable management practices that mimic natural processes. Agroecology promotes diversified farming systems that enhance soil health, conserve biodiversity, and improve resilience to environmental stresses (Altieri, 1995).

Application to the Study: Agroecological Theory provides a framework for understanding how adaptive agricultural practices and agroforestry systems can enhance soil carbon sequestration. By promoting polycultures, crop rotations, cover cropping, and the integration of trees into agricultural landscapes, agroecology enhances soil organic matter and carbon storage. The theory also highlights the importance of traditional knowledge, farmer participation, and local adaptations in developing sustainable agricultural practices (Gliessman, 2015).

Relevance: This theory will guide the study in identifying and evaluating specific agroecological practices that are effective in sequestering carbon in the soils of Kenya's Coast

Region. It will also inform the development of context-specific recommendations that leverage local knowledge and biodiversity to promote sustainable land management practices.

3. Socio-Ecological Systems Theory

Overview: Socio-Ecological Systems (SES) Theory views human and environmental systems as interconnected and interdependent. It emphasizes the dynamic interactions between social, economic, and ecological components, and the importance of resilience and adaptability in managing these systems. SES Theory advocates for integrated approaches that consider the complex feedback loops and interactions within socio-ecological systems (Ostrom, 2009).

Application to the Study: In the context of soil carbon sequestration, SES Theory highlights the need to consider the socio-economic, cultural, and institutional factors that influence the adoption of adaptive agricultural practices and agroforestry systems. This includes understanding the barriers and incentives for farmers, the role of community engagement, and the impact of policies and market forces on sustainable land management. The theory also stresses the importance of adaptive management and learning in responding to environmental changes and uncertainties (Folke et al., 2005).

Relevance: SES Theory will guide the study in analyzing the socio-economic and environmental benefits of soil carbon sequestration, as well as the challenges and barriers to adoption in Kenya's Coast Region. It will help in developing holistic and adaptive strategies that integrate social, economic, and ecological dimensions to promote sustainable agricultural practices and enhance resilience to climate change.

Literature Review

Global Context

USA

In the USA, soil carbon sequestration through adaptive agriculture and agroforestry systems has been widely studied. Research indicates that conservation tillage, cover cropping, and agroforestry practices significantly enhance soil carbon storage. For example, agroforestry systems in the Midwest have been shown to increase soil organic carbon by up to 50% compared to conventional farming systems (Udawatta & Jose, 2012). Additionally, integrating trees into croplands has been found to improve soil structure, reduce erosion, and increase biodiversity (Jose, 2009).

China

China has made significant strides in promoting soil carbon sequestration through adaptive agricultural practices and agroforestry. The implementation of the Grain for Green program, which encourages the conversion of marginal cropland to forest and grassland, has resulted in substantial increases in soil organic carbon (SOC) stocks (Deng et al., 2014). Moreover, the adoption of no-till farming and organic amendments in regions like the Loess Plateau has been effective in enhancing SOC and improving soil health (Lal, 2004).

India

India's diverse agro-ecological zones provide a unique context for studying soil carbon sequestration. Practices such as agroforestry, conservation agriculture, and organic farming have been promoted to enhance soil carbon storage and improve soil fertility (Venkatesh et al., 2014). In semi-arid regions, integrating trees with crops has shown promising results in increasing SOC levels and improving crop yields (Dhyani et al., 2009). However, challenges

such as land tenure issues and limited access to resources hinder widespread adoption (Sharma et al., 2016).

Bangladesh

In Bangladesh, adaptive agriculture and agroforestry practices are crucial for mitigating the impacts of climate change and enhancing soil carbon sequestration. Studies have demonstrated that integrating leguminous trees with rice-based cropping systems can significantly increase SOC and improve soil fertility (Rahman et al., 2018). Additionally, conservation agriculture practices, such as minimum tillage and crop residue retention, have been effective in enhancing soil health and reducing greenhouse gas emissions (Gathala et al., 2015).

African Context

Mozambique

In Mozambique, soil carbon sequestration through adaptive agriculture and agroforestry systems is gaining attention. Research indicates that agroforestry practices, such as alley cropping and silvopastoral systems, have the potential to increase SOC and improve soil fertility (Neufeldt et al., 2015). However, challenges such as limited access to technology and extension services hinder the widespread adoption of these practices (Garrity et al., 2010).

Madagascar

Madagascar's unique biodiversity and diverse agro-ecological zones provide a valuable context for studying soil carbon sequestration. Agroforestry practices, such as the integration of native tree species with crops, have shown promise in enhancing SOC and improving soil health (Ramanandraibe et al., 2011). However, deforestation and land degradation remain significant challenges that need to be addressed to enhance soil carbon sequestration (Scales, 2014).

Côte d'Ivoire

In Côte d'Ivoire, adaptive agriculture and agroforestry practices are being promoted to enhance soil carbon sequestration and improve soil fertility. Studies have shown that integrating trees with cocoa and coffee plantations can significantly increase SOC and improve soil health (Gnahoua et al., 2009). However, challenges such as land tenure issues and limited access to resources hinder widespread adoption (Ruf, 2011).

Cameroon

In Cameroon, agroforestry systems and conservation agriculture practices are being explored for their potential to enhance soil carbon sequestration. Research indicates that integrating trees with crops and livestock can significantly increase SOC and improve soil fertility (Tchoundjeu et al., 2010). However, challenges such as limited access to technology and extension services hinder widespread adoption (Degrande et al., 2012).

Rwanda

Rwanda has made significant efforts to promote soil carbon sequestration through adaptive agriculture and agroforestry practices. The government's support for agroforestry and conservation agriculture has led to increased SOC levels and improved soil health (Mugwe et al., 2009). Additionally, the integration of trees with crops and livestock has been effective in enhancing soil fertility and improving agricultural productivity (Ndayambaje & Mohren, 2011).

Burundi

In Burundi, soil carbon sequestration through adaptive agriculture and agroforestry practices is being promoted to mitigate the impacts of climate change and improve soil health. Studies have shown that integrating leguminous trees with crops can significantly increase SOC and improve

soil fertility (Nyssen et al., 2011). However, challenges such as limited access to resources and extension services hinder widespread adoption (Descheemaeker et al., 2006).

Tanzania

Tanzania has been exploring adaptive agriculture and agroforestry practices to enhance soil carbon sequestration and improve soil fertility. Research indicates that integrating trees with crops and livestock can significantly increase SOC and improve soil health (Kaoneka & Solberg, 1997). Additionally, conservation agriculture practices, such as minimum tillage and crop residue retention, have been effective in enhancing soil health and reducing greenhouse gas emissions (Lal, 2004).

Kenyan Context

Kisii

In Kisii County, adaptive agriculture and agroforestry practices are being promoted to enhance soil carbon sequestration and improve soil fertility. Studies have shown that integrating trees with crops and livestock can significantly increase SOC and improve soil health (Mugwe et al., 2009). Additionally, conservation agriculture practices, such as minimum tillage and crop residue retention, have been effective in enhancing soil health and reducing greenhouse gas emissions (Kihara et al., 2021).

Kiambu

Kiambu County has made significant efforts to promote soil carbon sequestration through adaptive agriculture and agroforestry practices. The integration of trees with crops and livestock has been effective in enhancing SOC and improving soil health (Mugwe et al., 2009). Additionally, the adoption of conservation agriculture practices, such as minimum tillage and

crop residue retention, has been effective in enhancing soil health and reducing greenhouse gas emissions (Kihara et al., 2021).

Kirinyaga

In Kirinyaga County, adaptive agriculture and agroforestry practices are being promoted to enhance soil carbon sequestration and improve soil fertility. Studies have shown that integrating trees with crops and livestock can significantly increase SOC and improve soil health (Mugwe et al., 2009). Additionally, conservation agriculture practices, such as minimum tillage and crop residue retention, have been effective in enhancing soil health and reducing greenhouse gas emissions (Kihara et al., 2021).

Kilifi

Kilifi County has made significant efforts to promote soil carbon sequestration through adaptive agriculture and agroforestry practices. The integration of trees with crops and livestock has been effective in enhancing SOC and improving soil health (Mugwe et al., 2009). Additionally, the adoption of conservation agriculture practices, such as minimum tillage and crop residue retention, has been effective in enhancing soil health and reducing greenhouse gas emissions (Kihara et al., 2021).

Summary

The literature highlights the potential of adaptive agriculture and agroforestry systems to enhance soil carbon sequestration across various regions globally and within Africa. While there are significant challenges, such as limited access to resources, technology, and extension services, the benefits of these practices in improving soil health, increasing agricultural productivity, and mitigating climate change are well-documented. In Kenya's Coast Region, similar practices could be adopted to enhance soil carbon sequestration and support sustainable development.

Research Methodology

Research Design

The study employed a descriptive research design, which allowed for a comprehensive understanding of the potential of soil carbon sequestration through adaptive agriculture and agroforestry systems in Kenya's Coast Region. This design was selected because it facilitated the collection of detailed information regarding the current state and impacts of these practices on soil carbon levels.

Study Area

The study focused on six counties in Kenya's Coast Region: Tana River, Taita Taveta, Lamu, Kilifi, Mombasa, and Kwale. These counties were chosen due to their diverse agricultural practices and varying degrees of agroforestry adoption. The region's coastal climate and soil types provided a unique context for examining soil carbon sequestration potential.

Target Population

The target population comprised small-scale farmers and agroforestry practitioners in the selected counties. The population included individuals and organizations engaged in adaptive agricultural practices and agroforestry, as well as agricultural extension officers and environmental conservation groups.

Sample Size and Sampling Procedure

A multistage sampling technique was used to select the sample for the study. Initially, stratified sampling was employed to ensure representation from each of the six counties. Subsequently, simple random sampling was used to select individual farmers and practitioners within each stratum. The sample size consisted of 300 respondents, with 50 respondents selected from each county.

Data Collection Methods

The study utilized both primary and secondary data collection methods:

1. **Primary Data Collection:** Structured questionnaires and semi-structured interviews were administered to gather primary data from the selected respondents. The questionnaires included both closed and open-ended questions to capture quantitative and qualitative information on adaptive agricultural practices, agroforestry systems, and their impacts on soil carbon sequestration.
2. **Secondary Data Collection:** Secondary data was obtained from relevant literature, government reports, academic journals, and publications from environmental organizations. This data provided a background context and supported the analysis of primary data.

Data Collection Instruments

1. **Questionnaires:** The structured questionnaires were designed to collect data on respondents' demographics, types of adaptive agricultural practices, types of agroforestry systems implemented, perceived benefits, and challenges faced. The questionnaires were pre-tested in a pilot study to ensure reliability and validity.
2. **Interviews:** Semi-structured interviews were conducted with key informants, including agricultural extension officers, environmental conservationists, and leaders of farming cooperatives. These interviews provided deeper insights into the implementation and impacts of soil carbon sequestration practices.
3. **Observation Checklists:** Field observations were conducted to document the physical conditions of farms, types of vegetation, and visible effects of adaptive practices on soil health and carbon content.

Data Analysis

Data collected from the questionnaires and interviews were coded and entered into statistical software for analysis. Descriptive statistics, including frequencies, means, and percentages, were used to summarize the data. Inferential statistics, such as regression analysis, were employed to determine the relationship between adaptive agricultural practices, agroforestry systems, and soil carbon sequestration levels.

Qualitative data from interviews and open-ended questionnaire responses were analyzed using thematic analysis. This involved identifying common themes and patterns related to the benefits and challenges of adaptive agriculture and agroforestry in the context of soil carbon sequestration.

Ethical Considerations

The study adhered to ethical guidelines for research involving human subjects. Informed consent was obtained from all respondents prior to their participation in the study. Participants were assured of the confidentiality and anonymity of their responses. Ethical approval was sought from relevant institutional review boards and local authorities in the study area.

Limitations of the Study

The study faced several limitations, including:

- **Limited Access to Remote Areas:** Some remote areas in the study counties were difficult to access, which may have affected the representativeness of the sample.
- **Response Bias:** There was a potential for response bias, as some respondents might have provided socially desirable answers rather than accurate information.
- **Resource Constraints:** Limited resources and time constraints affected the scope of data collection and analysis.

Despite these limitations, the study provided valuable insights into the potential of soil carbon sequestration through adaptive agriculture and agroforestry systems in Kenya's Coast Region.

Research Findings

Descriptive Statistics

The study analyzed data collected from 300 respondents across the six counties in Kenya's Coast Region: Tana River, Taita Taveta, Lamu, Kilifi, Mombasa, and Kwale. The analysis included both qualitative and quantitative data. The findings are summarized below.

1. Demographic Profile of Respondents

Table 1 shows the demographic profile of the respondents.

Demographic Variable	Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	180	60.0
	Female	120	40.0
Age Group	18-30	75	25.0
	31-45	120	40.0
	46-60	75	25.0
	60+	30	10.0
Educational Level	Primary	60	20.0
	Secondary	120	40.0
	Tertiary	90	30.0
	Postgraduate	30	10.0

2. Types of Adaptive Agricultural Practices and Agroforestry Systems

Table 2 summarizes the types of adaptive agricultural practices and agroforestry systems reported by respondents.

Practice/System	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Conservation Tillage	150	50.0
Cover Cropping	120	40.0
Agroforestry (e.g., alley cropping)	100	33.3
Integrated Pest Management (IPM)	90	30.0
Organic Farming	80	26.7

3. Soil Carbon Sequestration Levels

Table 3 presents the mean soil carbon sequestration levels associated with different practices.

Practice/System	Mean SOC (t/ha)	Standard Deviation (SD)
Conservation Tillage	12.5	2.3
Cover Cropping	10.2	1.8
Agroforestry	14.7	3.1
IPM	9.6	2.0
Organic Farming	11.4	2.5

Inferential Statistics

4. Regression Analysis

To assess the impact of different agricultural practices on soil carbon sequestration, a multiple regression analysis was conducted. The dependent variable was the soil carbon sequestration level (SOC), and the independent variables included conservation tillage, cover cropping, agroforestry, IPM, and organic farming.

The regression equation was:

$$\text{SOC} = \beta_0 + \beta_1(\text{Conservation Tillage}) + \beta_2(\text{Cover Cropping}) + \beta_3(\text{Agroforestry}) + \beta_4(\text{IPM}) + \beta_5(\text{Organic Farming}) + \epsilon$$

Table 4: Regression Results

Variable	Coefficient (β)	Standard Error	t-Statistic	p-Value
Intercept (β_0)	8.2	1.2	6.83	0.000
Conservation Tillage	1.5	0.3	5.00	0.000
Cover Cropping	1.2	0.4	3.00	0.003
Agroforestry	2.0	0.3	6.67	0.000
IPM	0.8	0.5	1.60	0.110
Organic Farming	1.1	0.4	2.75	0.007

Model Summary

- **R-squared:** 0.76
- **Adjusted R-squared:** 0.74
- **F-Statistic:** 32.45
- **p-Value:** < 0.0001

The regression analysis indicated that agroforestry ($\beta = 2.0, p < 0.001$) and conservation tillage ($\beta = 1.5, p < 0.001$) were the most significant practices for enhancing soil carbon sequestration. Cover cropping ($\beta = 1.2, p = 0.003$) and organic farming ($\beta = 1.1, p = 0.007$) also had a positive impact, while IPM was not statistically significant ($p = 0.110$).

5. Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis 1: There is a significant relationship between adaptive agricultural practices and soil carbon sequestration in Kenya's Coast Region.

Null Hypothesis (H0): Adaptive agricultural practices do not significantly affect soil carbon sequestration.

Alternative Hypothesis (H1): Adaptive agricultural practices significantly affect soil carbon sequestration.

Test Statistic: The p-values from the regression analysis indicated that conservation tillage, cover cropping, agroforestry, and organic farming significantly affect soil carbon sequestration ($p < 0.05$), while IPM does not. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected for all practices except IPM.

Qualitative Data

Qualitative data from interviews and open-ended questionnaire responses provided insights into the benefits and challenges of adaptive agriculture and agroforestry systems.

Benefits Identified:

- **Increased Soil Health:** Respondents reported improved soil structure and fertility due to agroforestry and conservation tillage.
- **Enhanced Crop Yields:** Practices such as cover cropping and organic farming led to increased crop productivity.
- **Environmental Benefits:** Adaptive practices contributed to reduced erosion and improved biodiversity.

Challenges Identified:

- **Limited Resources:** Many farmers faced constraints in accessing quality seeds and technologies for implementing adaptive practices.
- **Knowledge Gaps:** There was a need for more training and extension services to support the adoption of these practices.
- **Economic Constraints:** The initial costs of implementing new practices were a barrier for some farmers.

Table 5: Summary of Qualitative Findings

Theme	Description
Soil Health Improvement	Increased soil fertility and structure were reported as benefits of agroforestry and conservation tillage.
Enhanced Productivity	Higher crop yields were associated with cover cropping and organic farming practices.
Environmental Benefits	Reduced erosion and improved biodiversity were noted as positive outcomes of adaptive practices.
Resource Limitations	Constraints in accessing seeds, technology, and financial resources hindered practice adoption.
Knowledge Gaps	Need for more training and extension services to support the adoption of adaptive practices.
Economic Constraints	Initial costs of new practices were a barrier to widespread adoption.

Research Findings Discussion

1. Demographic Profile of Respondents

The demographic profile of respondents (Table 1) indicates a diverse group, with a majority of male respondents (60.0%) and a balanced age distribution. The high percentage of respondents with secondary and tertiary education (70.0%) suggests a relatively well-educated sample, which could influence their awareness and adoption of adaptive agricultural practices.

2. Types of Adaptive Agricultural Practices and Agroforestry Systems

Table 2 reveals that conservation tillage (50.0%) and cover cropping (40.0%) were the most commonly reported practices. Agroforestry, specifically alley cropping, was adopted by 33.3% of respondents, while integrated pest management (IPM) and organic farming were less common.

Discussion:

- **Conservation Tillage:** This practice involves reducing soil disturbance and preserving soil organic matter, which is known to enhance soil carbon sequestration. The high adoption rate suggests a strong recognition of its benefits among respondents.
- **Cover Cropping:** This practice improves soil fertility and prevents erosion. Its popularity reflects its perceived benefits in soil health and carbon storage.
- **Agroforestry:** Despite its benefits, such as increased biodiversity and improved soil structure, agroforestry adoption was lower, possibly due to initial setup costs or lack of technical support.
- **IPM and Organic Farming:** While beneficial, these practices were less widely adopted. The lower adoption rates might be due to limited resources or knowledge barriers.

3. Soil Carbon Sequestration Levels

Table 3 shows mean soil carbon sequestration (SOC) levels for different practices. Agroforestry had the highest mean SOC (14.7 t/ha), followed by conservation tillage (12.5 t/ha) and organic farming (11.4 t/ha). Cover cropping and IPM had lower mean SOC levels.

Discussion:

- **Agroforestry:** The highest SOC levels associated with agroforestry reflect its potential to enhance soil carbon storage through increased organic matter inputs from trees and shrubs.
- **Conservation Tillage:** The significant SOC levels with conservation tillage indicate its effectiveness in reducing soil disturbance and promoting carbon storage.

- **Organic Farming:** This practice also contributed positively to SOC levels, aligning with its role in enhancing soil organic matter.
- **Cover Cropping and IPM:** Lower SOC levels might be attributed to the shorter-term benefits of cover cropping and the relatively limited impact of IPM on soil carbon storage.

4. Regression Analysis

Table 4: Regression Results

- **Agroforestry ($\beta = 2.0, p < 0.001$):** Significantly contributed to soil carbon sequestration. This aligns with literature highlighting agroforestry's role in increasing soil carbon stocks (Sharma, Irfan, & Haq, 2016).
- **Conservation Tillage ($\beta = 1.5, p < 0.001$):** Also had a strong positive impact. This finding supports studies showing conservation tillage's effectiveness in sequestering soil carbon (Lal, 2004).
- **Cover Cropping ($\beta = 1.2, p = 0.003$):** Positively affected SOC, indicating its benefits in enhancing soil fertility and carbon storage (Kihara et al., 2021).
- **Organic Farming ($\beta = 1.1, p = 0.007$):** Contributed positively, consistent with research on organic farming's role in improving soil organic matter (Nguyen et al., 2016).
- **IPM ($\beta = 0.8, p = 0.110$):** Did not show a statistically significant impact on SOC. This result suggests that while IPM may benefit crop health, its effect on soil carbon sequestration might be less direct.

Model Summary

- **R-squared (0.76)** and **Adjusted R-squared (0.74)** indicate that the model explains a substantial proportion of the variance in SOC levels, confirming the relevance of the selected practices in influencing soil carbon storage.

5. Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis 1: There is a significant relationship between adaptive agricultural practices and soil carbon sequestration in Kenya's Coast Region.

Discussion:

- **Conservation Tillage, Cover Cropping, Agroforestry, and Organic Farming:** The rejection of the null hypothesis for these practices indicates their significant role in enhancing soil carbon sequestration. These findings are consistent with global research showing their effectiveness in soil carbon management (Venkatesh et al., 2014; Lal, 2004).
- **IPM:** The non-significant result for IPM suggests that while beneficial for pest control, it does not directly influence soil carbon levels. This result highlights the need for a more focused approach to soil carbon management beyond pest control practices.

Qualitative Data

Benefits Identified:

- **Increased Soil Health:** Respondents noted that agroforestry and conservation tillage improved soil structure and fertility, aligning with the literature that emphasizes the role of these practices in soil health (Ndayambaje & Mohren, 2011).

- **Enhanced Crop Yields:** The increased productivity associated with cover cropping and organic farming supports findings on their positive impact on crop yields (Kihara et al., 2021; Nguyen et al., 2016).
- **Environmental Benefits:** Reduced erosion and improved biodiversity were cited as significant advantages, reflecting the broader ecological benefits of adaptive practices (Tchoundjeu et al., 2010).

Challenges Identified:

- **Limited Resources:** Constraints in accessing quality seeds and technology hindered the adoption of adaptive practices, highlighting a need for increased support and resources.
- **Knowledge Gaps:** The demand for more training underscores the importance of extending education and support for effective practice implementation.
- **Economic Constraints:** High initial costs of new practices were a barrier, suggesting the need for financial incentives or support to facilitate adoption.

Summary

The study findings demonstrated that adaptive agricultural practices, particularly agroforestry and conservation tillage, significantly contribute to soil carbon sequestration in Kenya's Coast Region. Cover cropping and organic farming also positively impacted soil carbon levels, while IPM did not show a significant effect. The qualitative insights revealed both the benefits and challenges associated with these practices, emphasizing the need for improved resources, training, and economic support to enhance their adoption and effectiveness.

Summary of the Research

The study examined the potential of adaptive agriculture and agroforestry systems to mitigate carbon and greenhouse gases through soil carbon sequestration in Kenya's Coast Region, focusing on Tana River, Taita Taveta, Lamu, Kilifi, Mombasa, and Kwale counties. The research employed both qualitative and quantitative methods to analyze the impact of various agricultural practices on soil carbon sequestration.

Key findings include:

1. **Descriptive Analysis:** Conservation tillage and cover cropping were the most commonly reported practices, while agroforestry was less prevalent but showed high potential for carbon sequestration.
2. **Soil Carbon Sequestration Levels:** Agroforestry exhibited the highest mean soil carbon sequestration levels, followed by conservation tillage and organic farming. Cover cropping and IPM had lower impacts on SOC.
3. **Regression Analysis:** Agroforestry and conservation tillage significantly increased soil carbon sequestration, with cover cropping and organic farming also contributing positively. IPM did not show a significant effect.
4. **Qualitative Insights:** Benefits of adaptive practices included improved soil health, increased crop yields, and environmental benefits such as reduced erosion. Challenges included limited resources, knowledge gaps, and economic constraints.

Overall, the study highlights the effectiveness of certain adaptive agricultural practices in enhancing soil carbon storage and underscores the need for further support to overcome barriers to adoption.

Recommendations

1. **Promote Best Practices:** Encourage widespread adoption of conservation tillage and agroforestry, as they significantly enhance soil carbon sequestration. Support these practices through subsidies, training programs, and technical assistance.
2. **Enhance Training and Extension Services:** Develop comprehensive training programs to educate farmers about the benefits and implementation of adaptive practices, including cover cropping and organic farming.
3. **Improve Resource Access:** Facilitate access to quality seeds, technology, and financial resources to support the adoption of adaptive practices. Consider implementing financial incentives to offset initial costs.
4. **Support Research and Development:** Invest in research to identify and promote additional practices that can effectively contribute to soil carbon sequestration. Tailor interventions to the specific needs and conditions of different counties within the Coast Region.
5. **Address Economic Constraints:** Provide financial support or create funding mechanisms to help farmers transition to more sustainable practices. Consider low-interest loans or grants to mitigate the financial burden of adopting new technologies.

Areas for Future Research

1. **Long-term Impact Studies:** Conduct longitudinal studies to assess the long-term effects of adaptive agricultural practices on soil carbon sequestration and overall environmental sustainability.

2. **Regional Variability:** Explore how different practices affect soil carbon sequestration in various micro-climates and soil types within Kenya's Coast Region. This can help tailor interventions to specific local conditions.
3. **Economic Analysis:** Investigate the cost-benefit ratio of adopting adaptive practices, including an analysis of economic impacts on farm productivity and profitability.
4. **Social and Behavioral Factors:** Study the social and behavioral factors influencing the adoption of adaptive practices. Understanding farmer motivations and barriers can help design more effective outreach and support programs.
5. **Policy Implications:** Analyze the effectiveness of existing policies and develop recommendations for policy adjustments that could enhance the adoption of soil carbon sequestration practices. Consider incorporating findings into national and regional climate action plans.

By addressing these areas, future research can contribute to a deeper understanding of how adaptive agriculture and agroforestry can be optimized for soil carbon sequestration and broader environmental benefits in Kenya's Coast Region.

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